

An Implementation and Evaluation of PDF Password Cracking Using John the Ripper And Crunch

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Abstract: It can be challenging to choose the most effective word-mangling rules to apply while undertaking a dictionary-based password cracking attempt. We discuss a new method for generating password structures in the highest possibility order in this work. Based on a training set of previously revealed passwords, we first build an artificial probabilistic context-free grammar. As a result of this grammar, we can generate word-mangling rules and, as a result, password guesses for password cracking. By putting our tools and strategies to the test on genuine password sets, we will show that this strategy appears to be a more effective way to crack passwords than traditional methods. Our approach cracked 28 percent to 129 percent more passwords than John the Ripper, a publicly available standard password cracking software, in one set of testing. We'll construct a wordlist for dictionary attack using the Crunch tool.

Keywords – Kali Linux, Vulnerabilities, PDF, Crunch, John the Ripper, Bruteforce, Dictionary Attack.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Open-Source password security auditing and password recovery tool John the Ripper is available for a variety of operating systems. User passwords on Unix variants (Linux, *BSD, Solaris, AIX, QNX, etc.), macOS, Windows, "web apps" (e.g., WordPress), groupware (e.g., Notes/Domino), and database servers (SQL, LDAP, etc.) are all supported by John the Ripper jumbo. Captures of network traffic (Windows network authentication, WiFi WPA-PSK, etc.); encrypted private keys (SSH, GnuPG, cryptocurrency wallets, etc.); filesystems and discs (macOS.dmg files and "sparse bundles," Windows BitLocker, etc.); archives (ZIP, RAR, 7z); and document files (PDF, Microsoft Office's, etc.) These are only a few examples; there are plenty more.

In order to hack a password, we have to try a lot of passwords to get the right one. When an attacker uses thousands or millions of words or to crack a password, you must use a string of characters. There is no assurance that any of the millions of possible permutations will succeed. A wordlist is a collection of different combinations of characters. And, in order to crack a password or hash, we'll need a solid wordlist that can crack the password. So, with Kali Linux, we have a tool called crunch that we can use to achieve this. It's a tool for creating wordlists that comes pre-installed with Kali Linux. It's used to make

bespoke keywords using wordlists. It generates a wordlist that can then be better connect and merged. To make a wordlist, we might employ some specific patterns and symbols.

Fig. 1. Process flow of John The Ripper

was only natural to combine these two tools into one. It simplifies command-line options, speeds things up a little by employing a single framework instance, handles all potential output formats, and makes payload generation a little saner. It's a sophisticated set of tools for monitoring Wi-Fi network security. It emphasizes on several topics.

The information presented in this paper is only to be utilised in the appropriate manner and is not intended to lead to one becoming a hacker. The methods provided are intended to assist one in achieving specific goals related to penetration testing of one's own system or a system for which you have permission.

'John the Ripper' - Abbreviations

- Wordlist - A dictionary file that matches all of the terms in the dictionary to the password-protected pdf file.
- Hash - Using the john the ripper tool, the hash value of the password is determined.
- Exploit - Running malicious code to take advantage of a vulnerability.
- Metadata - The password-protected file's hash value is saved in the metadata of the pdf file.

- Rate of Process - If a dictionary attack is used, the time it takes to find a password depends on the wordlist, and if a brute force attack is used, the password length.

The hash value of the password of the password protected pdf file is generated using the john command in this problem concept, and the hash is applied to match with the dictionary file or to employ bruteforce assault of password combinations. When accessing the John the Ripper console, you could use following commands :

- help (which brings up some of the basic commands).
- back (this will allow you to go back to the john>).
- info (this will get info about a specific exploit to see where or not you want to use it).
- show (this will let you see all the available details for that specific file).
- info (this will show you info on the selected pdf).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Rubidha Devi.D, R. Venkatesan, and Raghuraman.K [1] present data retrieval methods in which the attacker has direct access to the database of the underlying applications. The attacker's intent, weaknesses, and assumptions are being used to characterize the attack.

Umesh Timalisina and Kiran Gurung [2] a summary- The number of malicious mobile apps targeting Android-based handsets is steadily increasing. Furthermore, these malicious apps are capable of downloading modules from servers controlled by criminal individuals, resulting in the activation of unexpected events within cellphones. As a result, the attacker can use the john tool to acquire unauthorised access to personal information and data kept on a smartphone by getting access with other tools and compromising the phone's passwords using either a Brute force assault or a Dictionary attack.

Michael D. Moore [3] examine the Android architecture, as well as the dangers and security flaws that exist. To mitigate known vulnerabilities, identify various attack mitigation techniques. A thorough examination will assist us in identifying existing flaws and will provide strategic direction for making the Android operating system more secure. The Linux kernel underpins the Android operating system. Because of its programmable and open nature, attackers are enticed to take advantage of it. Developers can easily access and edit source code on the Android platform. However, it also raises the risk of a security breach. As a result, john can simply compromise credentials by utilising the framework's capability.

The proposed system, according to Voitovych O.P, Yuvkovetskyi O.S, and Kupershtein L.M.[4], is a Blind Time Based SQLi that uses a time delay that is customised for different database answers. It is feasible to extrapolate certain information based on the time it takes to receive a server response. The response time can be greatly influenced by the server load and network speed.

Annie Chen [5] explains the concept of using various password guessing tools and ways to convert passwords to hashes and compare them to unknown passwords.

Tiwari Mohini et al. [6] Among all Smartphone operating systems, Android has the largest market share. One of the primary worries of today's Smartphone consumers is security. Smartphones have become more vulnerable to virus and malware threats as their capability and functionality have grown. Android may be more secure than any other smartphone operating system available today. The lack of developer limitations on Android raises the security risk for end users. In this study, we looked at application-level security as well as security challenges with a pdf file's less secure password.

III. PROBLEM DEFINITION

To find the password of a password protected pdf file using John the Ripper tool and Crunch tool. Crunch tool is used for generating word list for password cracking and it can be used for dictionary attack. Using the John tool we can find the hash value of the password of the password protected pdf file and it will be matched with the password string given by user either by brute force attack or dictionary attack. In here I will implement how to find the password of a pdf file using Crunch and John The Ripper tool.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

1) Wordlist Generation

To get started, open up a terminal. Crunch is already installed and ready to go on Kali, so you can just run it. For the first list, start with something small, like the one below.

Fig. 2. Generating wordlist using crunch

Crunch <min> <max> [options]

- Where min and max are numbers.
- Options denote the character set, output, etc.

```
kali@kali:~$ crunch 10 10 -t anurag%% -o dictfile.txt
Crunch will now generate the following amount of data: 110000 bytes
0 MB
0 GB
0 TB
0 PB
Crunch will now generate the following number of lines: 10000
```

Fig. 3. Example for wordlist generation

In here, we are generating a wordlist of 10000 words.

- 10 : It denotes the Min and Max length of the words.
- -t : It Denotes that we are using the following characters a to z.
- Anurag%% : It Denotes that the wordlist starting with anurag and ends with 4
- -o : Output is to be stored in a file.
- dictfile.txt : The output is stored in this file.

2) Password Hash Generation

```
kali@kali:~$ sudo john pdf1.hash
Using default input encoding: UTF-8
Loaded 1 password hash (PDF [MD5 SHA2 RC4/AES 32/64])
No password hashes left to crack (see FAQ)
kali@kali:~$ sudo john --show pdf1.hash
Desktop/protected.pdf:Anurag1998
1 password hash cracked, 0 left
```

Fig. 4. Finding hash of password protected pdf file

We gathered the hash of the password of the encrypted pdf file using the john tool and saved it in the pdf1.hash file. MD5, SHA2, and RC4/AES 32/64 can all be used as hashes.

We shall locate the hash in this article, which is used to match passwords from a dictionary file or to use a brute force assault.

After you've accomplished your goal, access the pdf file with the password you generated using the application.

V. METHOD OF IMPLEMENTATION

1) Brute Force Method

- It consists of an attacker submitting many passwords or passphrases with the hope of eventually guessing a combination correctly.
- The attacker systematically checks all possible passwords and passphrases until the correct one is found.

- Using the hash value generated, we can match it with different random passwords or passphrases.
- It will search through all the possible combinations of characters.
- It takes too much time when the password of the file is larger in length.

```
kali@kali:~$ sudo john pdf1.hash
Using default input encoding: UTF-8
Loaded 1 password hash (PDF [MD5 SHA2 RC4/AES 32/64])
No password hashes left to crack (see FAQ)
kali@kali:~$ sudo john --show pdf1.hash
Desktop/protected.pdf:Anurag1998
1 password hash cracked, 0 left
```

Fig. 5. Finding password of pdf file – bruteforce method

2) Dictionary Attack

- In this mode, we contains lists of common passwords to guess a given password.
- Dictionary file is mainly a text file consisting of some passwords.
- We will match all the passwords in the dictionary file with the hash which we generated from the pdf file.
- If it matches then it will shows the password.
- Otherwise Not Found will be prompted.

```
kali@kali:~$ sudo john --wordlist=Desktop/pass.txt sen.hash
Using default input encoding: UTF-8
Loaded 1 password hash (PDF [MD5 SHA2 RC4/AES 32/64])
Cost 1 (revision) is 3 for all loaded hashes
WILL run 0 OpenMP threads
Press 'q' or Ctrl-C to abort, almost any other key for status
anurag1998 (Desktop/sen.pdf)
1g 0:00:00:00 DONE (2021-12-07 05:51) 100.0g/s: 204800p/s: 204800c/s: 204800C/s anurag1792 .. anurag2046
Use the "--show --format=PDF" options to display all of the cracked passwords reliably
Session completed
```

Fig. 3. Finding password of pdf file – dictionary method

In here, the dictionary file pass.txt is used as a dictionary file and John the Ripper will take each and every word from the file and take its hash value and try matching with the hash value of password protected file is stored. If any match found, then it will display the password. Here the password is **anurag1998**

VI. RESULT

As a result, with this two problem concept the passwords of the pdf can be easily find using this tools. So we need it to secure the password of the pdf file with a high secrecy.

By this result every users beware of this kind of attacks on files and also devices with password and in any operating systems, it is possible to attack. So the users have to follow some of the preventions mentioned here:

PREVENTIONS

- Don't use small passwords.
- Don't use only letters for passwords.
- Don't show the password to anyone while you opening your file.
- Don't allow downloading any apps from cloud websites.
- Don't install apps with unknown resources enabled option.
- Use antivirus in a mobile device to keep an eye on every moment of mobile.
- Don't click any random link Never download unwanted apk file from unknown source.
- Always confirm with source pertaining to file to double sure
- Use numbers, alphabets and symbols for password.

VII. CONCLUSION

Finally, the John framework is a strong tool for gaining access to password-protected files and a distant target workstation. The ever-increasing necessity for patching vulnerabilities in the system or files can be treated with a great deal of information about them and the risk of an attack occurring by exploiting a particular vulnerability, with more than 900 attacks obtained by numerous combinations of john framework tools and exploit kinds.

The approach discussed in this paper defeats Hash detection and other methods of determining the file's password. This framework allows you to attack any password-protected files and password-protected operating systems such as Windows, Mac OS X, and Linux, as well as construct web payloads such as php, asp, jsp, and war. In the same way, it generates script payloads such as python, bash, pearl, and others.

This attack can also be carried out on the public network utilising a public IP address and a port forwarding router. One of the most important things to know is that devices connected to the same LAN can be hacked. Malware designed to circumvent anti-virus detection will continue to evolve, as will anti-virus detection approaches. The purpose of John's team's evasion module was to prevent detection by conventional anti-virus software.

VIII. FUTURE WORK

Because the Hash is placed in the metadata of the password-protected pdf file, the injection is now essentially manual. The automatic detection of hashes in PDF files may be found in the future. Then, using online mirror websites and phishing links, it's simple to target the devices or files automatically. Because it is automated, this version is much easier to use. When you download John Framework, it comes with an option to do all of

the exploitation on the browser using the computer as the local host. The John community was created to help bridge the gap between everyday penetration testers and folks who want to undertake the testing but don't know everything about it.

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